

Role Burnout in Mediation the Influence of Competence and Workload to Nurse Performance

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ABSTRACT

This research reveal burnout's role in mediate influence competency and work load to performance nurse at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital. Safety patient is priority main must implemented by the hospital, however, incident safety patients at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital happened. ideas that emerge is for convey importance competency and work load so that can reduce burnout so impact to performance nurse. This research use sample nurse data There are 100 executors working in the Inpatient Room of the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital. PLS- based SEM with approach quantitative as well as scale measuring from study previously used in this research. Competence influential negative and significant against burnout as well influential positive and significant to performance. workload influential positive and significant against burnout as well influential negative and significant to performance nurse. Burnout effect negative and significant to performance as well as burnout able mediate on influence not direct competency and work load to performance employee. This research gave important contribution, performance nurse tends determined by competence, so advised to provide facility development source human resources through seminars, workshops, training and development his education through gift permission task specific study taller in accordance with field knowledge, relationship existing training with task tree nurse.

KEYWORDS: Burnout, Competence, Workload, Nurse Performance

INTRODUCTION

Safety patient at hospital Then become issue important because many cases medical errors that occur in various countries. In America nearly 100,000 patients are treated at hospital die consequence medical error, besides That research also proves that death consequence injured medical 50% of them Actually can prevented (Cahyono, 2017). A number of researchers has measurement to culture safety patient in some Hospital in the world. Research results at home hospitals in Utah and Colorado show that there is incident no desired (Adverse Event) of 2.9%, of which 6.6%. died, while in New York mention that happen Unexpected Events (KTD) of 3.7% with number mortality 13.6%. Death rate consequences of adverse events in patients take care hospitalizations in America, amounting to 33.6% million per year ranging from 44,000-98,000. XXI Persian Congress in 2018 8 report that incident patient falls on the moon January until september 2018 by 14%, this makes presentation patient fall including to in the top five incident medical besides medical error (Committee Safety Hospital Patient, 2021).

Incident Data Safety Patients in Indonesia show in 2015 there is 114 reports incident congratulations patient, 2019 9 as many as 103, and in 2020 as much 1 34 and 20 21 years show enhancement incident safety reported patients as much 1 37 incidents. Provenca Java east occupy order highest 27% of them eleven provenca others (Banten 22.6%, DKI Jakarta 16.8%, Central Java 13.1%, West Java 8%, Riau 3.7%, Lampung 2.2%, Bali 1.5%, South Sumatra 0, 7%, North Sumatra 0.7%, South Sulawesi 0.7%, South Kalimantan 0.7%. type incident out of 137 incidents, 55.47% were Unexpected Events (KTD), 40.15% Occurrence barely Injuries (KNC). 8.76% resulted death, 2.19% injured irreversible (permanent), 22.17% injured reversible (temporary), and 19.71% injured light (Committee Safety Hospital Patient, 2021).

Provincial Psychiatric Hospital located in Bangli Regency as one of the providers of health services, especially mental health services, is the only Mental Hospital in the Province of Bali so that it is the main hope of the community to get quality mental health services. The Bali Provincial Mental Hospital has a capacity of 400 beds providing inpatient services

for adults, inpatient children and adolescents, psychogeriatric inpatient care, psychosocial rehabilitation, drug rehabilitation, outpatient care, physiotherapy, laboratories, and others. The Provincial Mental Hospital has a Hospital vision, namely to Become a Referral for Main Mental Health Services and Education with International Standards with the Nangun Sat Kerthi Philosophy Towards Atma Kertih Lan Jana Kertih. Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital is one Hospital type soul A who has implementing a safety program patient since year 2015. In PMK No. 129 of 2008 concerning Standard Hospital Minimum Services that happening incident safety patient the standard is 0% or 100% no happened at hospital. However, incident safety patients in the Provincial Mental Hospital still happened.

Problem related safety patient must quick handling by the partied hospital. According to Mustikawati (2018), safety patient can obtaine when contributing factors to incident safety patient can minimized even avoided. Contributing factors to incident safety patient according to Hasibuan (2017) is characteristics individua, organization, trait base work, management, environment external, and the environment physical. Meanwhile, according to WHO in 2018 four very influential factor in incident safety patient, that is characteristics individual, organizational and managerial, cooperation team, competency and environment. Apart from causes the incident stated before, other causes of occurrence incident safety patient also put forward by Cooper & Clarke in 2013 namely stress on the spot work, burnout and patient safety culture (WHO, 2018).

Competency factor is one of the individual variables that can affect performance, relationships between competence employee with performance is very intimate and important once again, its relevance exists and is strong accurate, even employee if want to increase performance should have appropriate competence with task his job Mangkunagara (2018). The workload factor is one of the individual variables that can affect performance, this is in accordance with Bashir (2018) a person employees who have burden high work so will impact on its performance, which in the end impact to results work provided by the company. Every work done can give mental, physical and social impact so that give burden alone for someone who lives it. In each company or organization, each individual can give different reactions to burden the work he got. A number of employees can overcome Far more Good while others can suffer and destroy concentration in Work

application The safety of patients in mental hospitals is influenced by factors complaints of the high workload of personnel because RSJ patients have different characteristics from hospital patients in general. The behavior of mentally ill patients has different and varied signs and symptoms, in terms of social relations, not a few mental patients are difficult to invite to communicate verbally according to the existing stimulus (incoherent) or don't want to be spoken to at all and don't even want to meet other people, mental patients also have emotions and behaviors that cannot be accepted in a manner rational such as tantrums, hitting around objects, there are also patients who have low motivation to live so that patients do not

want to do self - care. The patient's diverse behavior demands that nurses as medical personnel who often make contact with patients have duties and responsibilities high responsibility so that nurses are at risk of experiencing burnout or fatigue

There is an incident related incident safety patients at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital show that set standards Not yet can fulfilled, as well indicate that there is Lots potential incident raises loss even threaten safety patient. This could be due to the implementation of patient safety target indicators that have not been carried out in accordance with established standards. based on problem and Research Gap above, the writer is interested in doing research on Burnout role In Me mediation Influence Competency and Workload on Nurse Performance at the Mental Hospital of the Province of Bali

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS FORMULATION

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) put forward by Ajzen and Fishben in 1988 explains that Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is a theory that predicts considerations in human behavior regarding the behavior carried out by individuals arising from the intention of the individual to behave and the intention individual is caused by several internal and external factors of the individual. Between one human being and another human being has differences, one of these differences is good and bad actions. Every action taken by an individual must have a background, purpose and impact on the individual doing it. Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) assumes that rational humans will use existing information in a manner systematically then understand the impact of the behavior before deciding to implement the behavior. This planned behavior explains that individual intentions to behave are influenced by attitudes toward behavior (attitude toward the behavior), subjective norms (subjective norms.), and perceived behavioral control (perceived behavioral control) owned individuals (Dale, 2018).

Competence

Competence literally comes from the word competence, which means ability, authority and skill. Competence in terms of etymology means in terms of excellence, expertise from the behavior of an employee or leader who has good knowledge, behavior and skills. Characteristics of competence, namely something that is part of personal character and becomes part of a person's behavior in carrying out a work assignment (Mangkunegara, 2018). Competence is an individual characteristic that underlies performance or behavior in the workplace. Performance at work is influenced by knowledge, abilities, and attitudes, as well as work style, personality, interests, basics, attitude values, beliefs and leadership style, (Wibowo, 2017).

According to Sudarmanto (20 1 8) revealed that there are three main components in the formation of competencies, namely:

1. Knowledge

Employee knowledge also determines the success or failure of the implementation of the tasks assigned to him. Employees who have sufficient knowledge increase the efficiency of the company.

2. Skills

This skill is very necessary for employees who have occupied certain positions, because these skills are in communicating, motivating and delegating. In addition to the knowledge and skills of employees, another thing that needs to be considered is the attitude and behavior of employees.

3. Attitude

Is a pattern of behavior of an employee in the role of carrying out duties and responsibilities in accordance with company regulations. if the employee has the nature of supporting the achievement of the organization, then automatically all the tasks assigned to him will be carried out as well as possible.

Workload

workload that is amount work borne/ charged by an organizational unit or office which is results multiplication time with amount work. (Health Law No. 39 of 20 16). workload is condition work and description deep work time certain must resolved (Munandar, 2018). Irwady (2017), stated that burden Work is the average number of activities work on time certain, consisting from burden Work physical, load Work psychological as well as time work.

Definition burden Work in study This is burden Work as difference between ability employee with demands accepted assignment. workload can form burden Work physical, load Work psychological as well as time work, which refers on the dimensions put forward by Irwady (2017).

Nurse workload indicators according to the RI Ministry of Health (20 17) are as follows:

1. Aspect physique

workload determined based on amount patient must treated and many nurse on duty in a unit or room. Levels it depends patient classified become three level that is level depending on the minimum/ mild, level depends partial/ partial, and patients with level depends full/ total.

2. Aspect psychological

Mental/ psychological aspects counted based on connection between individual, with nurse as well as with head room and connection between nurse with patient, which effect on performance and level productive nurse. Frequent consequences arise is job stress, which will lower motivation work and lower performance employee.

3. Aspect time Work

working time productive that is the number of hours worked productive can used employee in carry out task principal and function, based on description task and time carry out task additions that don't including in task anyway.

Burnout

Burnout that is stressful condition extreme psychology so that individual experience fatigue low emotional and motivational For work. Burnout can is consequence from chronic job stress (King, 2018). According to Maslach & Leiter (2018) argues that burnou is reaction emotion negative happened environment work, when individual the experience prolonged stress. Burnout is syndrome psychological covering fatigue, depersonalization and decline ability in do tasks routine like resulted anxiety, depression, or even can experience disturbance Sleep

Burnout is something form Fatigue caused by someone who is active too intense, have high dedication and commitment, activities too long and too much as well as looked needs, and wants they as matter both can cause individual the feel exists the pressures it provides donation more a lot in the organization (Farber, 2018). Indicator burnout

1. Emotional Exhaustion (Fatigue emotional)

Fatigue emotional be marked with prolonged fatigue Good in a manner physically, mentally and emotional. When workers feel their exhaustion tend behave good overextended in a manner emotional nor physical. They No capable finish problem them. Still feel tired though Already enough rest, less energy in do activity (Leiter & Maslach, 2018).

2. Depersonalization (Depersonalization)

Dimensions second in burnouts marked depersonalization with attitude cynical, inclined interesting self from environment work. Dimensions This called with depersonalization that is separate self from others, shows cold emotions, show reaction negative to the behavior of others, for example treat patient with not enough nice and easy angry. When the nurse tends cold, guard distance, inclined No want to involved with environment it works (Leiter & Maslach, 2018).

3. Personal Accomplishment (Self Achievement)

Dimensions third is achievements self experienced employees decline so that show feeling negative, no happy and less satisfied to his job. Achievements decreased self is also shown with results evaluation bad self, low connection interpersonal, loss enthusiasm, decline productivity and lack ability adapt (Leiter & Maslach, 2018).

Performance

Performance is results implementation something job, fine characteristic physical/material and non- physical/non-material (Nawawi, 2017). Whereas according to Wirawan (2018) performance is which output generated by functions or indicators something works or something profession in time certain. According to Mangkunegara (2018) performance is results work in a manner quality and quantity achieved by employee in carry out his job in accordance with not quite enough answer given to him. Performance can interprete as performance or effectiveness operational something organization and employees based on goals, standards and criteria that have set before. Performance refers to rate achievement shaping tasks A work employee. performance

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reflect how much good employee fulfil condition A job. Performance often misinterpreted as effort reflecting energy released (Simamora, 2017).

Performance Indicators in apply management safety patient according Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia (2017) which became reject measuring applicator management safety patient includes 6 activities or target as following:

1. Accuracy Identification Patient
2. Enhancement Effective Communication
3. Enhancement Necessary Drug Safety Beware (High-alert)

4. Certainty Right Location, Right Procedure, Exactly Patient Operation
5. Subtraction Risk Infection Related Health Services
6. Subtraction Risk Patient Fall

Hypothesis Models

The hypothetical model of the mediating impact of implementing patient safety on safety culture and communication and its effect on nurse performance in preventing patient safety incidents at the Bali Provincial Mental Hospital, as following:

Figure 1. Research Hypothesis Model

Based on the research hypothesis model above, the hypothesis in this study is as follows: (H_1) Influential competence negative to burnout, (H_2) Workload influence positive towards burnout nurse, (H_3) Competence has a positive influence on performance, (H_4) Workload have a negative influence on performance, (H_5) Burnout have a negative influence on nurse performance

RESEARCH METHOD

Data collection was carried out using a questionnaire. The population size in this study was 100 people an executive nurse who works in the Inpatient Room of the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital. The sampling technique used is the Non-Probability technique, namely purposive sampling something method For choose sample that has objective in a manner subjective.

The research questionnaire was prepared based on the results of studies and theoretical and empirical formations during the pre-research, first assessing the face and content validity, sentence and structure of each question through discussions with several staff at the Bali Provincial Mental Hospital. In the process, several improvements were also made to the content of the questions in the research instrument. Furthermore, the try out involved 30 respondents to ensure the level of validity and reliability of the research instrument before it was distributed to all intended respondents. If the research

instrument has been declared valid and reliable at this trial stage, then the research instrument is said to have good calibration for each variable measure studied. Then the research instruments were distributed directly to all target samples. Data obtained from the distribution of research instruments as a whole. Then examined, tabulated, filtered, and analyzed to answer and discuss research problems.

Analysis technique inferential used for test the empirical model and the proposed hypotheses in study this. The analytical technique used is an equation model structural (Structural Equation Modeling – SEM) based variances or component base SEM, which is known with Partial Least Square (PLS).

1. Structural Model Evaluation or internal models; The goodness of fit model is measured using R-square predictive relevance for structural models. Q-Square predictive relevance for structural models, measure how much good mark observation generated by the model as well as the estimation the parameters. The value of $Q^2 > 0$ indicates the model has predictive relevance uses the formula $Q^2 = (1 - [(1 - R_1^2) (1 - R_2^2)])$. Q^2 magnitude own mark with range $0 < Q^2 < 1$. Q^2 is increasing approach value 1 means showing that the model is getting ok.
2. Testing of hypothesis; Testing hypothesis done with the t statistical test (t-test). If deep testing This obtained p-value < 0.05 (level significance (α) = 5%, means testing

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significant. On the other hand, if $p\text{-value} > 0.05$ (5% alpha), means No significant. When results testing hypothesis on the outer model is significant, p This show that indicator looked at can used as a measuring instrument latent variable. Meanwhile, whenever results testing on the inner model is significant, then can interpreted that there is meaningful influence latent variable one to other latent variables.

3. Inspection effect mediation; Mediation model check this is in principle for know intervention variable mediation, whether prove mediate in a manner full (fully mediated) or in a manner partial (partially mediated) or no as variable mediation. This mediation model examination method follows the instructions of Hair et al. (2014), namely: Examine the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable in the model involving the mediating variable (effect A). Examine the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable in the model without involving the mediating variable (effect B). Examine the effect of the independent variable on the mediating variable in the model (effect C). Examine the effect of the

mediating variable on the dependent variable in the model (effect D).

Based on the results of examining the four effects above (effects A, B, C, and D), it can then be proven and intervened from the mediating variables with the following criteria:

1. If effects C and D are significant, but effect A is not significant, then mediation proven in a manner full (fully mediated) in the model.
2. If effects C, D, and A are significant, then mediation proven in a manner Partial (partially mediated) in the model.
3. If the path coefficient (standardized) for effect A is almost the same as the path coefficient for effect B, then mediation is not proven/supported in the model.
4. If either effect C or D is not significant, then mediation is not proven/supported in the model.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of tests carried out using the Smart PLS 3.0 application, an image of the research model can be presented as follows:

Figure 2
Full Structural Model (PLS Bootstrapping)

The results of testing the research hypothesis based on the picture above are as follows: Hypothesis Testing 1: Competence (X_1) proved to have a negative and significant effect to burnout (Y_1). This result is indicated by the path coefficient which has a negative value of -0.342 with a T-statistic = 4.358 (T-statistic > 1.96) and p value = 0.000 (p value < 0.05). Based on this, hypothesis 1 is declared accepted.

Hypothesis Testing 2: Workload (X_2) proved to have a positive and significant effect to burnout (Y_1). This result is

indicated by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.387 with T-statistic = 4.539 (T-statistic > 1.96) and p value = 0.000 (p value < 0.05). Based on this, hypothesis 2 is declared accepted.

Testing Hypothesis 3: Competence (X_1) proved to have a positive and significant effect on nurse performance (Y_2). This result is indicated by the path coefficient which has a positive value of 0.684 with T-statistic = 11.281 (T-statistic > 1.96) and

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p value = 0.000 (p value < 0.05). Based on this, hypothesis 3 is declared accepted.

Hypothesis Testing 4: Workload (X_2) proved to have a negative and significant effect to nurse performance (Y_2). This result is indicated by the path coefficient which has a negative value of -0.131 with T-statistic = 1.975 (T-statistic > 1.96) with p value = 0.049 (p value < 0.05). Based on this, hypothesis 4 is declared accepted.

Hypothesis Testing 5: Burnout (Y_1) proved to have a negative and significant effect to nurse performance (Y_2). This result is indicated by the path coefficient which has a negative value of -0.198 with T-statistic = 2.788 (T-statistic > 1.96) with p-value = 0.006. Based on hypothesis 5 it is declared accepted.

Burnout (Y_1) is able to mediate the indirect effect of competence (X_1) on nurse performance (Y_2). These results are shown from the mediation test that was carried out, it appears that the effects C, D and A have significant values as well the indirect effect path coefficient obtained is above 0.10, which is 0.112 (Hair et al, 2014). The results of this study determine that competence (X_1) can affect nurse performance through the role of burnout can be proven empirically. Based on these results it can be interpreted, the better the competency possessed, the lower the burnout experienced by nurses will be so that it will have an impact on increasing the performance of nurses in implementing patient safety in Mental Hospitals Bali Province. Other information that can be conveyed is that the mediating effect of the burnout variable has an indirect effect on competence on nurse performance partial. These findings provide an indication that the burnout variable (Y_1) is not a determining variable in the influence of competence (X_1) on nurse performance (Y_2) (Partially Mediated).

Burnout (Y_1) is able to mediate the indirect effect of workload (X_2) on nurse performance (Y_2). These results are shown from the mediation test that was carried out, it appears that the effects C, D and A have significant values as well the indirect effect path coefficient obtained is above 0.10, which is 0.117 (Hair et al, 2014). The results of this study determine that the workload (X_2) can affect the performance of nurses through the role of burnout can be proven empirically. Based on these results it can be interpreted, the lighter the workload of nurses then the burnout experienced by nurses will be low so that it will have an impact on increasing the performance of nurses in implementing patient safety in Mental Hospitals Bali Province. Other information that can be conveyed is that the mediating effect of implementing burnout variable (Y_1) on the indirect effect of workload on nurse performance partial. This finding indicates that the variable applying burnout (Y_1) is not a determining variable in the influence of workload (X_2) on nurse performance (Y_2) (Partially Mediated).

Competency track (X_1) on nurse performance (Y_2) has the greatest total effect, namely 0.796 compared to the workload path (X_2) on nurse performance (Y_2) which only gets a total effect of -0.248. These results provide an indication that the performance of nurses in implementing patient safety tends to be determined by the competencies implemented in the Mental

Hospital of the Province of Bali, this shows that the implementation safety patient related tightly with competence nurse in manage and deliver care safe care of patients.

Discussion

Influence Competence on Burnout

Based on results analysis about competence influence against burnout, shows that competence proved to have a negative and significant effect against burnouts. The results of this analysis show that hypothesis 1 (H_1) is accepted. Findings This give meaning the better the competency will reduce the burnout experienced by nurses because competence is another important factor that needs to be considered if the organization wants its employees not to experience burnout.

Provincial Psychiatric Hospital Bali is Hospital handling soul patient with disturbance psychology, which is different with Hospital in general, s already Certain care provided by nurses at home Sick This different with Hospital generally in nature matter communication with patient feels hard, besides That there are also some confessed nurse get violence from patient especially still patients tall level anxiety, so competence is needed in this case special skills in dealing with mental disorders, nurses who have good skills or skills in dealing with mental patients will not experience burnout at work because caring for mental patients is a responsibility that must be carried out according to the duty and function of nurses while nurses who have not have skill in handle patient soul will feel difficulty in give care nursing soul if, not yet adapt with duties and responsibilities answer the so that Not yet more believe self in do their duties so that nurses will be at risk of experiencing burnout.

Influence Workload on Burnout

Based on results analysis about influence workload to burnout, shows that workload proved to have a positive and significant effect to burnout, results testing This show that hypothesis 2 (H_2) is accepted. this result give meaning the lower the workload nurse will reduce the burnout experienced by nurses. This proves that excessive workload will not be a big problem if the procedures for managing work are carried out properly and support from leaders and colleagues in the form of togetherness, willingness, and social activity is carried out between nurses and family, friends, co-workers and superiors. In this study, nurses often carry out social activities with other people, such as having lunch with colleagues and superiors, taking time to gather with friends and family so that this can reduce the level of burnout that occurs in nurses.

The behavior of patients with mental disorders has different and varied signs and symptoms, in terms of social relations, not a few mental patients are difficult to communicate verbally according to the existing stimulus (incoherent) or do not want to be spoken to at all and do not even want to meet other people, mental patients also have emotions and behave that cannot accepted in a manner rational such as tantrums, hitting around objects, there are also patients who have low

motivation to live so that patients do not want to do self - care. The patient's diverse behavior demands that nurses as medical personnel who often make contact with patients have duties and responsibilities high responsibility so that nurses are at risk of experiencing burnout or exhausted.

Influence Competence on Nurse Performance

Based on results analysis about competence on nurse performance, shows that competence proved to have a positive and significant effect on nurse performance, results testing This show that hypothesis 3 (H₃) is accepted. This finding gives meaning the better the competence possessed by nurses will improve performance of nurses in the implementation of goals patient safety. Patient safety is one of the values to ensure continuity complete health services in the hospital. Patient safety as a service does not hurt the patient nor the patient care system in a safer hospital. risk measurement, identification and management of patient health, recording and measurement cases, case learning and implementation of actions and solutions to reduce risk. Nurse who has skills or skills, knowledge and behavior which is good will can Work with well, give service to patients with well, so condition This can push enhancement performance nurse at the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital.

Burnout Impact In Mediating the Influence of Competence Against Nurse Performance in Implementing Patient Safety Goals based on results analysis shows that burnout able to mediate on the indirect influence of competence on the performance of nurses in implementing patient safety. The results of this study indicate that competence can affect nurse performance through the role of burnout can be proven empirically. Based on these results it can be interpreted, the better the competency possessed, the lower the burnout experienced by nurses will be so that it will have an impact on increasing the performance of nurses in implementing patient safety in Mental Hospitals Bali Province. Other information that can be conveyed is that the mediating effect of the burnout variable has an indirect effect on competence on the performance of nurses in implementing patient safety is partial where the variables burnout is not a determining variable on the influence of competence.

Influence Workload on Nurse Performance

Based on results analysis about workload against nurse performance, shows that workload proved to have a negative and significant effect to nurse performance in implementing patient safety, results testing This show that hypothesis 4 (H₄) is accepted. this result give meaning the lower the workload nurse will improve nurse performance in implementing patient safety. This proves that a light workload can improve performance because the ability of nurses is up to standard work, there is support from leaders and colleagues.

Burnout Impact In Mediating the Effect of Workload on Nurse Performance in Implementing Patient Safety Goals Based on results analysis show burnout is able to mediate the indirect effect of workload on the performance of nurses in

implementing patient safety. The results of this study determine that the workload can affect nurse performance through the role of burnout can be proven empirically. Based on these results it can be interpreted, the lighter the workload of nurses then the burnout experienced by nurses will be low so that it will have an impact on increasing the performance of nurses in implementing patient safety in Mental Hospitals Bali Province. Other information that can be conveyed is that the mediating effect of the burnout variable has an indirect effect on the burden on nurse performance is partial, meaning that burnout is not a determining variable in the effect of load Work on nurse performance.

Influence Burnout on Nurse Performance

Based on results analysis about burnout effect to nurse performance, shows that burnout proved to have a negative and significant effect to nurse performance in implementing patient safety, results testing This show that hypothesis 5 (H₅) is accepted. This result gives meaning that the lighter the nurse's burnout will increase nurse performance in implementing patient safety. Application safety patient held or done with Good so service priority optimal safety and quality will be gives that impact broad. Especially for public will get more service quality, safe and fulfill hope them. Share hospital become mark plus for achievement standard service national and international. Safe and secure service quality too expected can increase trust public to Hospital. For power health can grow values new especially important application safety patient in every activity service provided.

Experienced nurse fatigue or burnout, deliver impact to depersonalization in others especially patient, often feel tired, no capable carry out task or the job with good and true, as well start reluctant for do job. Condition already critical will bring up desire for leave work or switch to profession other. Moderate nurse experience burnout will hinder performance and being No aligned with vision and mission Hospital place Work so that hinder enhancement quality service and improvement degrees health patient

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Conclusions this research are: Competence has a negative and significant effect against burnouts. this result give meaning that the better the competency will reduce the burnout experienced by nurses; Workload positive and significant effect against burnouts. this result give meaning that the lower the workload nurse will reduce the burnout experienced by nurses; Competence has a positive and significant effect on nurse performance. this result give meaning that the better the competence possessed by nurses will improve nurse performance in implementing patient safety. Burnout able to mediate on the indirect influence of competence on nurse performance; Workload has a negative and significant effect on nurse performance. this result give meaning that the lower the workload nurse will improve nurse performance in

implementing patient safety. Burnout is able to mediate on the indirect effect of workload on nurse performance; Burnout has a negative and significant effect to nurse performance. this result give meaning the more that the lighter the nurse's burnout will increase nurse performance in implementing patient safety.

Suggestion

Suggestions this research are: Organizing training technical nursing on an ongoing basis both organized by internal and external institutions other institutions that have linkages with field service health; Providing human resource development facilities through seminars, workshops, training and educational development, especially in mental health nursing through granting permission to study assignments specifically higher according to the field of knowledge, training related to the main duties of nurses; Avoid there are multiple tasks that make the employee's workload excessive so that can work optimally; The leadership of the Bali Province Psychiatric Hospital is necessary do effort system rotation for nurse in room maintenance so that No raises boredom in nurses if work on one room in period long time can raises stress; Increase the ability of nurses to balance internal and external loads, namely separating the workload on the family (home) with the workload when performing nursing services at the hospital; Providing rewards to officers who excel in implementing patient safety by providing opportunities to attend training and education as well as assigning services based on performance; Conduct family gathering activities so that the relationship between the leadership and the nurse's family can be closer; The hospital can also make nurses feel comfortable inside work by making the work environment more comfortable for nurses feel relaxed at work

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